

ACCOUNTING SKILLS FOR SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT OF SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES IN NIGER STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract: The need for sustainable development is one of the key driving forces of the rapid changes and numerous challenges in today's economic world. Also, putting accounting skills in the context of sustainable development is logically possible. This paper, therefore, examined the accounting skills needed by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) for sustainable economic development using Niger State of Nigeria as a focal point. The paper adopted the descriptive research design approach and data were generated from professionals and owners of SMEs in the state through a structured questionnaire. The data analysis was conducted by means of the mean scores and standard deviations of the respondents. The hypotheses were tested using the t-test statistics and the results showed that T-cal. of 2.50 was greater than the T-table value of 1.96 (T-cal. 2.50 > T-table 1.96) at 0.05 level of significance, this implies that the results showed that the owners of SMEs were of different opinions regarding the accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State for sustainable development, thereby rejecting Ho1. Also, the T-cal. of 0.97 was less than the T-table of 1.96 (T-cal. 0.97 < T-table 1.96) at 0.05 level of significance in (Ho2). Therefore, Ho2 was not rejected indicating that owners of SMEs were of the same opinion regarding the benefits of acquiring accounting skills. The paper concludes that the acquisition of accounting skills by owners of SMEs is of utmost importance given the numerous contributions that are inherently accruable to owners and operators of SMEs especially in developing nations. The paper recommends that owners of SMEs should endeavour to employ staff that has basic accounting skills.

Keywords: Accounting Skills, Sustainable Development, Small and Medium Scale Enterprises.

INTRODUCTION

The precise professional expertise and active participation of accountants in risk management, business analysis, decision support, due diligence, anti-corruption activities as well as ensuring adequate transparency help accountants globally in reconsidering their responsibilities which arose due to business sustainability and sustainable development goals. Also, sustainable development has become very important following the need to

achieve economic growth without harming the earth's natural resources as well as meet the needs of the present and future generations.

More so, accounting profession is an important element in achieving sustainable economic development as it is a science that helps in the process of making accurate economic decisions at various levels. Information provided by accounting regarding sustainable development had been formed as a result of monitoring impacts and outcomes of the cash-flow and such information are vital for the sustainable development globally. Therefore, such information should be clear and understandable by all employees of the Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs); available on time; suitable to decision makers' needs; comparable; distinguishable and verifiable. (Alsawalhar & Hamdan, 2020).

In Niger State, most of the jobs, especially those in non-urban areas are provided by SMEs. However, SMEs in Niger State struggle to gain access to fundamental accounting skills that are needed in a timely manner for improved productivity, profitability, customer satisfaction and improved cycle time. It is for this reasons that this paper which centers on accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State for sustainable development is specifically undertaken, to:

1. Determine the accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State for sustainable development and
2. Determine the benefits accruable to the SMEs that acquire proper accounting skills.

Against the backdrop of the two specific objectives of this study, the study hypothesized that:

Ho1: There is no significant difference between the mean scores of the responses of owners of SMEs on the accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State.

Ho2: The mean scores of the responses of owners of SMEs have no significant difference with the benefits of acquiring proper accounting skills for sustainable development in Niger State.

REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Accounting Skills and Sustainable Development

Onoh (2011) stated that accounting skills are those competencies in basic accounting required by a person to function competently, confidently, and successfully in the process of carrying out one's function of recording daily business transactions, which include skills in book-keeping, purchasing and supply, bargaining, determining labour costs, simple budgeting, keeping of accurate receipts, sales records skills in keeping reliable records, sourcing for market outlets, work in progress records, credit purchases, invoices, cheque payments, keeping customers' records and goods inventory. Others are skills in good credit facility practices, operating the cash payment receipts, cash sales, prudent financial and working capital management.

Furthermore, Osuala (2004) opined that the knowledge of accounting skills is very imperative for sustainable business growth. The non-possession of these accounting skills by SMEs, therefore, constitutes a problem such that, the chances of survival of the business are slim and the probability of imminent collapse become high. The knowledge of accounting skills by SME will promote in them good financial management, which is aimed at

ensuring that there is adequate cash on hand to meet the necessary current and capital expenditures as well as to assist in maximizing growth and profits. It requires knowledge of liquidity management. Management of money demands that the SME owner/ manager must need to plan for all his future need for funds, plan for the most economical way of acquiring funds from different sources and be able to also plan for the most efficient way of putting to use acquired money from friends, family members, banks and other sources. The capacity and competencies required to prepare the accounting records are the basic accounting skills being studied in this paper. More so, Nwokike (2010) stated that no business activity could be successfully operated without the assistance of the accounting skills; this is because procurement and spending of money are involved. The development and appreciation for accounting functions such as skills to keep fundamental accounting records and its use is so important to the SME owners and managers to the extent that without it, the SMEs owners can get up one day to discover that the working capital has been used up. The result of this could be such that the owners of SMEs can no longer pay salaries of their staff, cannot replace equipment, cannot purchase raw materials as consumables and can no longer pay for other utility services. Acquisition of accounting skills by SME owners and managers will boost their operational efficiency. Also, the acquisition of fundamental accounting skills will imbue on SMEs owners a favourable disposition to prudently manage their enterprises in the most profitable way.

Small and Medium Enterprises and Sustainable Development

Small enterprises are those enterprises whose total assets (excluding land and buildings) are above Ten Million Naira (₦10,000,000) but not exceeding One Hundred Million Naira (₦100,000,000) with a total workforce above ten, but not exceeding forty-nine employees whereas medium enterprises are those enterprises whose total assets (excluding land and buildings) are less than Ten Million Naira (₦10,000,000) with a workforce not exceeding ten employees (Bello, Bayu, Adamu, Ogboji & Lass, 2021). On the other hand, CBN (2020) defines SMEs as organizations with an annual turnover of less than One Hundred Million Naira turnover per annum with less than three hundred employees.

Furthermore, the SMEs make up a vital part of Nigeria's business system because in Nigeria, the SMEs provide the most important vehicle for both the government and large scale enterprises to thrive. Also, the SMEs are more commonly involved in trading, provision of services and craft-production activities, they therefore contribute significantly to the national economy and growth by the volume of employment they provide to the citizenry and by the amount of tax revenues they remit to the national coffers. However, there is most often the issue of how much tax liability to be paid by these SMEs. The tax authorities often reject the returns and accounts prepared by these SMEs and label them as incorrect because it is believed that the SMEs lack the capacity, the skills and proficiency to prepare accounts and returns to meet the requirements of the tax authorities. Also, inadequate accounting records are kept by most SMEs resulting in incorrect revenues and expenditures which affect their growth and sustainability. There is therefore the need to evaluate the accounting skills needed for sustainable

development of the SMEs in Nigeria, especially in Niger State as a result of the role of job provision in the state and their contributions to the state economic development.

More so, SMEs are believed to be the engine room for the development of any economy because they form the bulk of business activities in a growing economy like that of Nigeria, and in line with this, Mukaila (2011) stated that SMEs contribute to improved living standards, bring about substantial local capital formation, achieve high level of productivity, and creation of jobs at relatively low capital cost, especially in the fast growing service sector. Also, Belal (2013) opined that SMEs are vehicles for the reduction of income disparities thus developing a pool of skilled or semi-skilled workers as a basis for the future industrial expansion, improve forward linkages between economically, socially and geographically diverse sectors of the economy which will lead to sustainable development. SMEs also offer excellent breeding ground for entrepreneurial and managerial talents to thrive.

However, sustainable development is a development idea that provides that in living and meeting their present needs, humanity should not compromise the capability of future generations in meeting their own needs. It is a manner in which societies are organized for their continual existence over a relatively long period, taking into consideration the current and future needs of humanity such as preserving the environment as well as social and economic concerns (Youmatter, 2020). Makarenko and Plastun (2017) stated that high corporate reporting which is an aspect of accounting skill ensures financial stability, sustainable development, and achieving sustainable development goals specifically. Accountants do these by measuring, evaluating, and disclosing the improvement in sustainable development goals achieved by firms generally but specifically by SMEs.

METHODOLOGY

The study adopted descriptive survey method. The survey was used because it involves the assessment of a group which represents the entire population. The population of the study was 318 registered owners of small and medium enterprises in Niger State. 80 owners of SMEs were purposively selected based on their location within the state. Structured questionnaire was used to collect the necessary data for the study. The questionnaire consisted of two sections. Section one consisted of personal data, while section two consisted of items derived from the content of the research objectives. It contained thirty (30) questionnaire items [nineteen (19) items relating to objective one and eleven (11) items relating to objective two]. A four-point response scale of strongly agreed (SA), agreed (A) disagreed (D), and strongly disagreed (SD) was used for the data collection. The respondents were asked to indicate their degree of agreement or disagreement with the statements contained in the instrument. The instrument was validated by two experts, in the fields of accounting and entrepreneurship. As a pilot study, twenty-two copies of the questionnaire were administered to twenty-two owners of small and medium scale enterprises in Kogi State to establish the reliability of the instrument. The reliability was established using Cronbach Alpha and the data yielded reliability coefficient of 0.89 thus, indicating that the instrument was reliable and suitable for use for this study.

Out of the eighty (80) copies of the questionnaires administered, sixty five (65) were correctly filled and returned showing a return rate of 81.25%. The data analysis and results were therefore based on the returned questionnaire. The data collected was collated and analyzed using mean with standard deviation. The null hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance using t-test statistics. The decision rule implies that items with mean value of 2.50 and above were regarded as agreed while items with mean values below 2.50 were regarded as disagreed.

Analysis and Interpretations

Results of the data analyzed for this study were presented according to the research objectives and contained in Tables 1 and 2.

Research Objective 1: The accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State

Table 1: Mean responses of respondents on the Accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State, Nigeria

S/ No	Accounting Skills	SA	A	D	SD	— X	SD	DECISION
1.	Skills to keep reliable records	33	17	10	5	3.20	0.97	Agreed
2.	Ability to prepare simple ledgers	5	40	20	-	2.77	0.58	Agreed
3.	Skill to keep imprest	35	30	-	-	3.54	0.50	Agreed
4.	Skill in accurate book-keeping	15	40	10	-	3.08	0.62	Agreed
5.	Ability to prepare budgets	12	34	11	8	2.78	0.90	Agreed
6.	Ability to keep daily cash receipts	26	19	13	7	2.98	1.02	Agreed
7.	Ability to keep cash sales records	38	22	5	-	3.51	0.64	Agreed
8.	Ability to use accounting software	4	16	35	10	2.22	0.78	Disagreed
9.	Ability to synthesize data	5	20	30	10	2.31	0.83	Disagreed
10.	Skill of communication	18	32	13	2	3.02	0.78	Agreed

11.	Ability to keep credit purchases records	15	40	10	-	3.08	0.62	Agreed
12.	Skill in keeping records of invoice	29	24	9	3	3.22	0.86	Agreed
13.	Ability to keep accurate accounting records	21	36	5	3	3.15	0.75	Agreed
14.	Skill in keeping analysis books	24	37	4	-	3.31	0.58	Agreed
15.	Ability to keep credit sales records	12	46	5	2	3.04	0.62	Agreed
16.	Ability to handle double entry bookkeeping system	6	34	15	10	2.55	0.87	Agreed
17.	Skill in preparing product waybills	3	39	14	9	2.55	0.79	Agreed
18.	Inventory control skill	10	10	35	10	2.31	0.92	Disagreed
19.	Skill in financial management	5	33	20	7	2.55	0.79	Agreed
	Grand Mean and Standard Deviation					2.90	0.76	

Source: Researcher's computations 2024

Table 1 shows the listed responses on the accounting skills needed by small and medium scale enterprises for sustainable development. The mean scores ranges from 2.22 to 3.54 with standard deviation ranging from 1.02 to 0.50. The result indicates that 16 out of 19 items agreed that SMEs need fundamental accounting skills for sustainable development. These items are 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,10,11,12,13,14,15,16,17,19. Also, the items 8, 9 and 18 disagreed. A grand mean of 2.90 and standard deviation of 0.76 are also recorded for the nineteen items indicating that all the respondents generally agreed to the fact that SMEs need accounting skills for sustainable development in Niger State ($2.90 > 2.50$).

Research Objective 2: The benefits of acquiring accounting skills by SMEs

Table 2: Mean scores of the respondents on benefits of acquiring accounting skills

S/ No	Benefits of Accounting Skills	SA	A	D	S D	— X	SD	DECISION
1.	Boost business activities	15	40	10	-	3.08	0.62	Agreed
2.	Provide basis for investment to owners of SMEs	10	30	20	5	2.69	0.83	Agreed
3.	Help owners of SMEs to maximize profits	11	43	7	4	2.94	0.73	Agreed
4.	Promote the preparation of feasibility reports	15	35	5	10	2.85	0.96	Agreed
5.	Enhance creativity and innovation	11	44	10	-	3.02	0.57	Agreed
6.	Enhance good financial management	32	24	9	-	3.35	0.72	Agreed
7.	Promote the acquisition of comprehensive knowledge of the business	-	49	10	6	2.66	0.64	Agreed
8.	Enable owners of SMEs to make good decisions	18	37	4	6	3.03	0.85	Agreed
9.	Enable owners of SMEs to keep adequate and accurate records	35	20	5	5	3.31	0.92	Agreed
10.	Enable owners of SMEs to identify areas of inefficiencies and wastages of resources	5	25	35	-	2.54	0.64	Agreed
11.	Enhance understanding of growth of business such that fluctuation in business cycle is correctly interpreted	14	19	20	12	2.54	1.03	Agreed
	Grand Mean and Standard Deviation					2.91	0.77	

Source: Researcher’s Computations 2024

Table 2 shows the mean responses of the respondents on the benefits of acquiring accounting skills for sustainable development. The mean scores range from 3.35 to 2.54 with the standard deviation ranges from 1.03 to 0.57. Also, from table 2, all the listed items on benefits of acquiring accounting skills were agreed. The grand mean of

2.91 and standard deviation of 0.77 indicate complete agreement by the respondents. This shows that all the respondents overwhelmingly agreed that the benefits of accounting skills in SMEs in Niger State will enhance sustainable development ($2.91 > 2.50$).

Hypotheses Testing

The hypotheses formulated for the study were tested using the t-test statistical analysis at 0.05 level of significance.

Hypothesis one

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of the responses of owners of SMEs on the accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State, Nigeria

Table 3: T-test analysis of accounting skills

Sample Size	\bar{X}	SD	df	T-cal.	T-table	Decision
65	2.90	0.76	65	2.50	1.96	Reject Ho1

Source: SPSS computation

The data presented in table 3 shows a computed T-cal. of 2.50, which indicated that, the respondent-owners of SME's opinion is greater than the T-table value of 1.96 (T-cal. of $2.50 > T$ -table of 1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis Ho1, of no significant difference was rejected. The decision shows that the owners of SMEs were of different opinion regarding the accounting skills needed by SMEs in Niger State for sustainable development.

Hypothesis two

The mean scores of the responses of owners of SMEs have no significant difference with the benefits of acquiring accounting skills for sustainable development in Niger State, Nigeria

Table 4: T-test analysis of benefits of accounting skills to SMEs

Sample Size	\bar{X}	SD	df	T-cal.	T-table	Decision
65	2.89	0.77	65	0.97	1.96	Do not reject Ho2

Source: SPSS computation

The computed T-cal. of 0.97 is less than the T-table of 1.96 (T-cal. of $0.97 < T$ -table of 1.96) at 0.05 level of significance. Therefore, the null hypothesis, Ho2 will not be rejected indicating that owners of SMEs were of the same opinion regarding the benefits of acquiring accounting skills.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The findings from research objective one showed the accounting skills needed by small and medium scale enterprises that will enhance their business acumen and improve their profit margin. These skills include skills in keeping fundamental accounting records as accurate book keeping, cash payment receipts, cash sales, credit sales records, skill in inventory control, ability to use basic accounting software, skill in financial management and ability to prepare simple ledger. Other skills that were revealed in the study include, skill in synthesizing data, skill in keeping accurate accounting records, skill in demonstrating simple budgeting, skill in preparing product waybill, skills in handling double entry book-keeping, receipt records as well as viable credit purchase records. The degree of agreement by owners of SMEs showed that fundamental accounting skills are needed by them for operational efficiency and maximization of profit in their self-employment efforts. The findings are in agreement with Agbata, Okaro and Onyeogubalu (2022) who posited that acquisition of accounting skills by managers of small and medium scale enterprises enhances their business acumen and thereby making them to have a comprehensive knowledge of business. Adams (2020) emphasized that the possession of accounting skills will consolidate and enhance SMEs businesses as well as eliminate early failure. Furthermore, the result from research objective two showed the benefits of acquiring accounting skills. The result revealed the enormous benefits derivable in acquiring accounting skills for sustainable development as revealed by a grand mean of 2.91. The result revealed that the owners of SMEs overwhelmingly agreed that the benefits of accounting skills are numerous, which is in line with the studies by Agada (2018) and Modish (2022) who also agreed that the acquisition of accounting skills will enable SMEs to function competently, confidently, profitably, and successfully in the process of carrying out their daily business transactions.

CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of this study, it was concluded that the acquisition of accounting skills by owners of SMEs is of utmost importance given the numerous contributions that are inherently profitable to owners of SMEs. Furthermore, accounting skills will enhance and promote the managerial stability of owners of SMEs as they will become well informed in keeping the fundamental accounting records for effective profitability of their businesses. Accounting skills are inevitable skills needed by every owner of small and medium scale enterprises.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Owners of SMEs should endeavour to employ staff that has basic accounting skills
2. A strong awareness campaign should be embarked upon by appropriate government organs to sensitize owners of SMEs on the need for acquiring accounting skills.
3. The appropriate government organs and agencies should organize free seminars and workshop for owners of SMEs at intervals.

4. Owners of SMEs should endeavour to acquire accounting skills that will promote the quality of their products and upgrade their services.

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